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“OUR LIVES”

Whatever happens with both our lives
We'll be together until the day we die
Never letting go, never saying goodbye
So glad to be here, kicking and alive

Do you remember our laughs and cries
I remember how you wiped your tears and smiled
Time can only fade it in my mind
But in my heart it will forever shine
It's our memories, it's our lives

Whatever tomorrow holds
Our love story, let it be told
Never let it go, never let it fold
Today until we both grow old

It's amazing how time flies by
Now, we're together as husband and wife
With our son, Gryffyn John
We sail through life, hand in hand
Creating memories, living out our lives